

Gas thermodynamics from the SZ effects

Stefania Amodeo

Université de Strasbourg, CNRS, Observatoire astronomique de Strasbourg, UMR 7550,
F-67000 Strasbourg, France
email: stefania.amodeo@astro.unistra.fr

Abstract. The thermodynamic properties of the ionised baryons in galaxies, groups, and clusters encode the effects of the assembly history and feedback processes that shape galaxy and cluster formation. These properties can be studied through the thermal and kinematic Sunyaev-Zel'dovich (SZ) effects imprinted on cosmic microwave background maps, measured for individual clusters or from stacking analyses. I present SZ cross-correlation measurements from ACT and *Planck*, with high signal-to-noise measurements of the electron density, temperature and pressure distribution around a sample of galaxy groups. I discuss the impact of the modelling uncertainties and I present our constraints of the baryonic processes like the feedback and the non-thermal pressure support, as well as the effect of including baryons in the modelling of galaxy-galaxy lensing measurements. These measurements provide novel tests of hydrodynamical simulations with sub-grid physics models. I finally outline the rapid growth of SZ cross-correlation measurements expected over the next decade.

Keywords. Cosmic Microwave Background – Cosmology: Theory – Galaxies: Clusters: General – Galaxies: Formation

1. Introduction

The Sunyaev Zel'dovich effects (SZ, Sunyaev & Zeldovich 1972) are powerful probes of the circumgalactic medium (CGM) and intracluster medium (ICM). As cosmic microwave background (CMB) photons propagate through the expanding universe they are scattered by energetic electrons in the ICM and CGM, resulting in temperature fluctuations which are dominant on arcminute scales: i) the inverse Compton scattering of the CMB photons with the hot thermal gas causes a distortion in the CMB temperature, known as thermal SZ effect (tSZ), which is proportional to the integrated electron pressure; ii) the scattering of the CMB photons by the free electrons having bulk motion relative to the CMB rest-frame causes a shift in the CMB temperature proportional to the integrated electron momentum, known as kinematic SZ effect (kSZ). By measuring these fluctuations we can determine the thermodynamic history of baryons around galaxies and clusters (see Mroczkowski et al. 2019, for a recent review of the SZ effects).

2. SZ cross-correlation measurements

The tSZ and kSZ are measured through cross-correlations that use observations from high-resolution CMB experiments combined with observations from surveys of the large scale structure (optical, near-infrared) that allow either photometric or preferably spectroscopic redshift measurements. In Schaan et al. (2021) we used a combination of CMB maps from the Atacama Cosmology Telescope (ACT) and *Planck* (Naess et al. 2020) in two frequency bands, 98 and 150 GHz, and the CMASS galaxy sample (Ahn et al. 2014), a large catalog of galaxies which roughly trace the center of groups with halo mass of $\sim 3 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$, and redshift $0.4 < z < 0.7$. We measured the tSZ and kSZ by stacking

the signal of the CMB maps at the positions of the galaxies, and obtaining radial profiles in the range $1 < R/R_{\text{vir}} < 4$ by applying aperture photometry filters. We obtained a major advancement in the kSZ detection with a significance of 6.5σ (against the null hypothesis), and a gas density profile unambiguously more extended than dark matter profile, meaning that most baryons fall outside the virial radius. We also measured the tSZ and gas thermal pressure profile (10σ). In Amodeo et al. (2021) we analysed these measurements to constrain the gas thermodynamics and the properties of feedback inside galaxy groups. We developed a pipeline, `Mop-c GT` (“Model-to-observable projection code for Galaxy Thermodynamics”) † that projects theoretical profiles of gas density and pressure into kSZ and tSZ profiles so that they can be directly compared to observations. We explored the impact of different modelling uncertainties and found that important factors are using theoretical profiles that match the mass distribution of the observed sample, include the two-halo term, i.e. the contribution of surrounding halos and convolving the projected profiles with the characteristic beam profiles of the instrument (Moser et al. 2021). Our models also include a correction for the contamination of the tSZ signal by the thermal emission of dust from galaxies in our sample, which we estimate from ACT (98, 150 GHz) and Herschel/H-ATLAS data (600, 857, and 1200 GHz, Eales et al. 2010). The combination of kSZ and tSZ data provides the most powerful constraints on the baryonic processes like feedback and non-thermal pressure support in the CGM or ICM. We performed a joint fit of the kSZ and tSZ data to a polytropic gas model originally proposed by Ostriker et al. (2005). The model assumes that the gas is in pressure equilibrium with the total gravitational potential, and the density and total pressure profiles follow a polytropic equation of state. The total pressure is the sum of a thermal and a non-thermal component, where the latter has a radial profile described by a power law. Our results showed an upper limit for the amplitude of the non-thermal pressure profile, indicating that less than 20% of the total electron pressure within the virial radius is due to a non-thermal component. The model also accounts for some energy injected into the gas by AGN and superbovae feedback processes, and we robustly estimated that this is 30% of the total binding energy of the system. The good signal-to-noise ratio of the SZ measurements on a wide radial range allowed us to study the gas density and pressure profiles in the group-sized CMASS halos at intermediate redshift ($z \sim 0.6$). We characterised amplitude and shape of fully parametric (generalized Navarro-Frenk-White) models for the gas density and thermal pressure (Zhao 1996; Battaglia et al. 2012) and we evaluated the impact of our findings on galaxy formation and cosmology as discussed below.

3. Implications and Perspectives

Baryons impact the matter power spectrum and any observable that depend on the matter power spectrum especially on the small, non-linear scales. There are lensing models (Saito et al. 2016) for the CMASS sample that are calibrated to match the large-scale clustering of galaxies, while they are discrepant from actual observations from the lensing signal in the same galaxies (Leauthaud et al. 2017). This is known as “lensing is low”, and it’s an open problem today. In Amodeo et al. (2021), we estimated the baryon correction to the galaxy-galaxy lensing model signal using our best fit density profile of the CMASS sample from the kSZ measurements. Our estimate reduces the difference between the original theoretical model and the weak-lensing galaxy cross-correlation measurements in Leauthaud et al. (2017) by 50% at most, but does not fully reconcile it.

† <https://github.com/samodeo/Mop-c-GT>

Other possible effects that can explain the discrepancy are measurement systematics, sample selection, assembly bias, or extensions to our concordance cosmological model.

Cosmological simulations have been extremely successful on the past decade in reproducing the observable stellar properties of the galaxies, such as the stellar luminosity function and red/blue fraction. Since these simulations do not resolve enough scales to perform *ab initio* calculations of crucial physical processes in galaxy evolution, such as star formation and various energetic feedback mechanisms, they require physically motivated sub-grid modelling schemes. The predicted density and pressure profiles from Illustris TNG (Springel et al. 2018) match the SZ data in Amodeo et al. (2021) below the virial radius, while at larger radii the simulations, especially for the pressure profile, are significantly lower. Previous comparisons between simulations and thermal SZ profiles have been mostly limited to higher masses, like galaxy clusters (e.g. Planck Collaboration et al. 2013), where the simulations matched the observations across a large range in radii. This implies that the current sub-grid models for energy injection and numerical method for propagation are sufficient at describing the ICM but do not sufficiently heat the CGM at radii beyond the virial radius.

To conclude, the studies presented here show that cross-correlation measurements of tSZ and kSZ effects can be used to study the baryon distributions in the CGM, particularly in environments with low densities and in the outskirts of galaxy groups, where they are able to reveal information about assembly histories and feedback processes. In the near future, the significance of the SZ measurements will greatly improve with: i) CMB experiments performed with higher sensitivity, larger sky and frequency coverage such as the Simons Observatory, CCAT-Prime, CMB-S4; ii) larger galaxy sample from spectroscopic surveys of the large-scale structure like the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI), the Vera Rubin Observatory and Euclid. Battaglia et al. (2017) presented forecasts on the kind of constraints we will be able to achieve with current CMB experiments and a DESI-like spectroscopic survey of $\sim 10^6$ galaxies. In particular, we expect a significant improvement in the kSZ detection, from the current SNR of ~ 7 to ~ 100 , allowing to measure of the thermodynamic profiles at the percent level precision. Further improvements with the next generation CMB-S4 experiments will enable more detailed studies across multiple sub-samples of mass, redshift, and galaxy properties.

References

- Ahn, C. P., Alexandroff, R., Allende Prieto, C., et al. 2014, *ApJS*, 211, 17
 Amodeo, S., Battaglia, N., Schaan, E., et al. 2021, *Phys. Rev. D*, 103, 063514
 Battaglia, N., Bond, J. R., Pfrommer, C., et al. 2012, *ApJ*, 758, 75
 Battaglia, N., Ferraro, S., Schaan, E., et al. 2017, *JCAP*, 2017, 040
 Eales, S., Dunne, L., Clements, D., et al. 2010, *PASP*, 122, 499
 Leauthaud, A., Saito, S., Hilbert, S., et al. 2017, *MNRAS*, 467, 3024
 Moser, E., Amodeo, S., Battaglia, N., et al. 2021, *ApJ*, 919, 2
 Mroczkowski, T., Nagai, D., Basu, K., et al. 2019, *Space Sci. Revs*, 215, 17
 Naess, S., Aiola, S., Austermann, J. E., et al. 2020, *JCAP*, 2020, 046
 Ostriker, J. P., Bode, P., & Babul, A. 2005, *ApJ*, 634, 964
 Planck Collaboration, Ade, P. A. R., Aghanim, N., et al. 2013, *A&A*, 550, A131
 Saito, S., Leauthaud, A., Hearin, A. P., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 460, 1457
 Schaan, E., Ferraro, S., Amodeo, S., et al. 2021, *Phys. Rev. D*, 103, 063513
 Springel, V., Pakmor, R., Pillepich, A., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 475, 676
 Sunyaev, R. A. & Zeldovich, Y. B. 1972, *Comments on Astrophysics and Space Physics*, 4, 173
 Zhao, H. 1996, *MNRAS*, 278, 488